

Fermat's Principle and Quantum Bound States

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In a previous note (1) we argued that Fermat's principle of least time is present in the photon wave dispersion relationship $E=pc$ which may be written as $0 = -Et+px$ with $x/t=c$. We argued that a nonzero constant $= -Et+px$ applies to a free particle with rest mass, but that Fermat's principle is still present. Furthermore the form $-Et + px$ implies the existence of a frequency and wavelength for both a photon and free particle with rest mass. (Interestingly $-Et+px$ is both the free particle relativistic action $-m_0 \int \sqrt{1-vv/cc}$ and nonrelativistic $.5m_0 \int v v$ with $c=1$ and $v=x/t$.) Fermat's principle implies that $d/dx \rightarrow$ momentum (x component) as discussed in(1). An eigenfunction $\exp(ipx)$ demonstrates wave behaviour of a free particle with rest mass. In (1) we argued that if one knocks out a quantum bound particle it will be in a state $\exp(ipx)$. Thus this wave type information should also be included in the bound state so we postulated a bound state represented by $W(x) = \text{Sum over } p \ a(p)\exp(ipx)$ (i.e. a wavefunction) such that the Fermat result $d/dx \rightarrow p$ still holds.

In this note we wish to consider the idea of a statistical equilibrium and the concept of a constant energy. In the case of refraction it seems a complicated statistical scattering process occurs which slows down the motion of a photon i.e. c changes to c/n where n is the index of refraction. Thus one piece of information, namely n , describes the complicated statistical process as in thermodynamics. If E (energy) remains constant $p \rightarrow pn$. Thus in this complicated statistical scenario a $\cos(-Et+pn x)$ electric field pattern remains but $p \rightarrow pn$ i.e the wavelength has changed. The idea of a constant energy may even be applied to light scattering from a mirror moving with a constant v in the negative y direction. The actual energy and momentum of the incident and reflected rays are not equal, but for E_1 special $= p_1 v(\text{relative } 1)$ and E_2 special $= p_2 v(\text{relative } 2)$ with $v(\text{relative } 1) = c - v\cos(A)$ and $v(\text{relative } 2) = c + v\cos(B)$ where A and B are angles of incidence and reflection measured with respect to the y axis. E_1 special $= E_2$ special.

In this note we retain the idea that a particle knocked from a quantum single particle bound state is described by $\exp(ipx)$ in keeping with Fermat's principle. We consider the bound state to still have waves as Fermat's principle suggests $d/dx \rightarrow p$, but they cannot be of the same height and width because of the changing value of $V(x)$ with x (i.e. the potential). According to Newton's law one has conservation of energy i.e. $pp/2m + V(x) = E$, but we consider this to apply to a $p(\text{rms}) = m v(\text{rms})$ in the Schrodinger equation.

If the forms $\exp(ipx)$'s are to be retained within the bound quantum state (i.e. this information is not lost) and one has a constant E (energy) then the potential must be modified statistically to allow for the idea of conservation of energy for each p , but must also represent a constant potential to retain the form of $\exp(ipx)$. Thus in short the Schrodinger equation becomes a weighted sum of $\exp(ip(j) x)$ functions with each having a different wavelength (like refraction), but interacting with different constant potentials to ensure that E remains constant for each $p(j)$.

In other words we think of a potential $V(x)$ as a statistical set of refraction discontinuities i.e. impulses which produce $\exp(ipx)$'s which are like light moving through a homogeneous medium i.e. a momentum eigenstates. For this to happen, however, the various $\exp(ipx)$'s need to combine with $V(x) = \text{Sum over } k \ V_k \exp(ikx)$ terms to create a $V_{\text{modified}}(p) \exp(ipx)$ where $V_{\text{modified}}(p)$ is a constant because each free particle $\exp(ipx)$ is associated with a different

effective potential and a kinetic energy $p^2/2m$, but the same energy E . We argue that this results from applying ideas of Fermat's principle to a particle with rest mass. Newton's picture of a particle accelerating i.e. $x(t)$ emerges if one considers rms values for which all information of $\exp(ipx)$ and crests/troughs of $W(x)$ are ignored. In particular, $W(x)$ =wavefunction may have crests and troughs, but $-1/2m d/dx dW/dx / W = KE(x)$ Newton which shows no crests or troughs, but simply balances $V(x)$ in $KE(x)+V(x) = E$.

Fermat's Principle

Fermat's least time principle may be applied to reflection/refraction problems. This involves extremizing time by taking a derivative with respect to an invariant spatial variable e.g. d/dx . " X " is invariant because there is no discontinuity in medium in its direction as mirror and medium surfaces lie in the x direction. This leads to a conservation of momentum equation in the direction of this variable i.e. $d/dx \rightarrow p$ (in the x direction). Creating an eigenfunction yields $\exp(ipx)$. In (1) we argue that $E=pc$ contains Fermat's principle if written as $0 = -Et + px$ (.e.g one may take d/dx). For a particle with rest mass we replace 0 with a constant (namely $-m_0c^2 t_0$), but Fermat's principle still applies because the derivative d/dx of a constant is 0 . Thus $d/dx \rightarrow p$ holds for a free particle as well. A particle with rest mass, however, acts under a potential according to: $p^2/2m + V(x) = E$. This seems to be very different from the behaviour of light and Fermat's principle. We suggest, however, that one may make the two compatible.

The idea of Fermat's principle applied to refraction i.e. a discontinuity in medium leading to an abrupt change in momentum with E remaining constant might at first seem very different from a particle with rest mass moving in a potential. From Newton's law the particle seems to accelerate i.e. $m dv/dt = -dV/dx$. Thus one thinks of $v(x)$ changing in x and t as one follows the particle. This happens because $V(x)$ is a function of x . If $V(x)$, however, could be thought of as an average form statistically delivering impulse hits then like with refraction one would have abrupt changes in momentum. We consider in the next section whether it is possible to have a superposition of refraction states $\exp(ipx)$ within such an impulse picture. One requires many states $\exp(ipx)$ because various momenta exist within the bound state. In fact as will be seen there may be more momentum states than actual $p(\text{rms})$ values where $p(\text{rms})^2/2m + V(x) = E$.

$V(x)$ is spatially dependent and $\exp(ipx)$ requires a constant potential. If $V(x)$ is written as $\sum_k V_k \exp(ikx)$ then it has terms which mimic $\exp(ipx)$. Each term $\exp(ikx)$ may deliver an impulse of k i.e. $\exp(ikx) \exp(ipx) = \exp(i(p+k)x)$. There is still the question of an $\exp(iKx)$ term associated with V_k , but this may be considered as part of normalization constant. In particular, Fermat's principle suggests that $d/dx \rightarrow p$. An eigenvalue equation is: $-i d/dx \exp(ipx) = p \exp(ipx)$. This equation, however, contains $\exp(ipx)$. If one only wishes to have numbers (as in Newton's conservation of energy equation) then $-d/dx \exp(ipx) / \exp(ipx) = p$. ((A)). It is possible, as shown in the next section, that a $V_k \exp(ikx)$ term may combine with an $\exp(i(p-k)x)$ term to yield an $\exp(ipx)$ which has the appearance of the denominator term $\exp(ipx)$ in ((A)). In fact if one replaces $-d/dx d/dx W(x) = p^2 W(x)$ and $W(x) = \sum_p a(p) \exp(ipx)$ one may include all kinds of refraction results $\exp(ipx)$'s and have the denominator term $W(x)$ combine

with $V_k \exp(ikx)$'s in different ways to lead to a sum of differently weighted constant new potential conservation equations, but with the same energy E_n .

Quantum Bound State and a Spatially Dependent Normalization Constant

A photon passing from a vacuum into a medium consisting homogeneously of certain molecules scatters statistically in a complicated manner. Given the homogeneity, however, one expects the photon to have the same form (i.e. eclectic field form) throughout. Furthermore one has the idea that the scattering uniformly changes the speed from c to c/n where n is a number greater than 1 which one may call the index of refraction. If E (energy) is to remain constant, then $p \rightarrow pn$ from $E=pc$. Thus the effect of the complicated statistical scattering is to change $\cos(-Et+px)$ into $\cos(-Et+pnx)$. In other words there is still a wavelength pattern, but the wavelength is not the same as in a vacuum.

In (2) we tried to apply this idea to a single bound quantum particle in a potential $V(x)$. We argued that instead of $\exp(ipx)$ one should have a function $W(x)$ with varying crests/toughs (i.e. with different heights and widths) because there is no longer spatial homogeneity due to the function $V(x)$ potential which varies in space. From Fermat's principle we still retain the idea that $d/dx \rightarrow p$.

In (2), however, we did not link $W(x)$ to $\exp(ipx)$ (free particle with rest mass) forms which should be manifest if the bound particle is knocked out of its bound state. If one only considers $W(x)$ and wishes to have conservation of energy on average with Fermat's idea $d/dx \rightarrow p$ then:

$$-1/2m \frac{d}{dx} \frac{dW/dx}{W} + V(x) = E \quad ((1))$$

((1)) is the Schrodinger equation which holds for discrete E values. The first term on the LHS has $W(x)$ in the denominator as a normalization constant which varies in space because unlike in the case of $\exp(ipx)$ or light one does not have spatial homogeneity because of $V(x)$.

For example, consider $\exp(ipx)$ i.e. $-1/2m \frac{d}{dx} \frac{d \exp(ipx)}{\exp(ipx)} + V(x) = E$. The same form is used in ((1)).

Keeping the Information of $\exp(ipx)$ in a Bound State

In (1) we argued that if a bound quantum particle (single particle system) is knocked out of the bound state it has the form $\exp(ipx)$ i.e. wave behaviour which describes diffraction and interference is manifest. We argued that this information does not simply appear when the particle is knocked out, but should be contained inside the bound state as well. Thus we suggested that:

$$W(x) = \text{Sum over } p \ a(p)\exp(ipx) \quad ((2))$$

One may argue that ((2)) is simply a Fourier series, but it is applied to a special function $W(x)$ such that $KE(x) =$ the first term on the LHS of ((1)). In general one may apply a Fourier series to any x function, but in this case we argue it is based on a physical reason.

The form ((2)), however, is unusual in that it contains spatially invariant (i.e. repeated hump) objects i.e. $\exp(ipx)$'s. This violates the idea of $V(x)$ which is not spatially invariant. Thus we suggest that $V(x)$ may be an average quantity i.e.:

$$V(x) = \text{Sum over } k \quad V_k \exp(ikx) \quad ((3))$$

This suggests an interfering set of $\exp(ipx)$'s which are like a combination of different "photons" in different refracting media. For a particle with rest mass, however, each $\exp(ipx)$ must be in a constant potential because $\exp(ipx)$ from ((1)) is a solution of $W(x)$ for a constant potential. We ask: How does this come about? We also note that a constant E for all x appears to be a statistical/thermodynamical parameter describing an equilibrium.

((3)) is the first step for allowing the formation of what seems to be a constant type potential for $\exp(ipx)$. We note first a similarity with refraction. When light moves from one medium to another there is a discontinuity in the index of refraction and p_1 changes to p_2 . This is like an impulse which occurs at this discontinuity point. We argue that:

$$\exp(ipx) \exp(ikx) = \exp(i(p+k)x) \quad ((4))$$

is not only an impulse changing p to $p+k$, but is like a refraction discontinuity.

If one writes ((1)) with $V(x)$ ((3)) and $W(x)$ ((2)) and collects terms with the same $\exp(ipx)$ (orthonormal) then:

$$-1/2m \frac{d}{dx} \frac{d}{dx} \exp(ipx) / \exp(ipx) + 1/a_p \text{ Sum over } k \quad V_k a(p-k) = E_n \quad ((5))$$

This is of the form of a constant potential acting on an $\exp(ipx)$, but this potential has been changed from $V(x)$ in order to ensure a constant E_n . One may note that a similar form holds for all p , but is statistical in nature in that for a single $\exp(ipx)$ one has the information of all other $\exp(i p(j) x)$'s including their weights $a(p(j))$. Nevertheless there seems to be a physical aspect to ((5)) in that it is associated with $V(x)$ representing an average potential which delivers impulse hits (as noted in (3)). These impulse hits are like changing from one refractive medium to another, but for a particle with rest mass requires a constant potential.

Consistency with Newton's Picture

The above approach differs from that of Newton's $.5m v(x) v(x) + V(x) = E_n$ which yields a $v(x)$ i.e. follows the particle in time: $x(t)$. $x(t)$, however, does not predict diffraction/interference. In the above we insisted on using $\exp(ipx)$ for a free particle so that diffraction/interference is predicted, but were then forced to incorporate $\exp(ipx)$'s in Newton's conservation of energy equation. One may note, however, that $KE(x)_{\text{Newton}} = -1/2m \frac{d}{dx} \frac{dW}{dx} / W(x)$ so that the

form $W(x) = \sum_p a(p) \exp(ipx)$ does lead to Newton's kinetic energy expression with a $v(\text{rms})(x)$. This $v(\text{rms})(x)$ may be written in terms of a $d x^1 / dt$ which is Newton's approach and does describe particles in a classical setting in which the wavelength is too small for diffraction/interference to be noticed.

Conclusion

In conclusion, we argue that Fermat's principle applied to refraction suggests $d/dx \rightarrow p$ and $E=pc$ with constant E suggests $p \rightarrow np$ where n is the index of refraction might also be used to try to describe a bound quantum particle. Such a particle is influenced by $V(x)$ which depends on x i.e. is not uniform in space like a refraction medium. With refraction, as light passes from n_1 to n_2 there is a discontinuity and a change in momentum. We argue that this is equivalent to an impulse hit for a particle with rest mass. Thus $V(x)$ may actually represent a statistical set of impulse hits which change an $\exp(ipx)$ (eigenfunction of $-id/dx$) into a different $\exp(ip_1 x)$. If $V(x)$ is written as $V(x) = \sum_k V_k \exp(ikx)$ one may show (as done above) that a quantum bound state is superposition of refraction type states and that one may obtain a series of conservation equations for various $\exp(ipx)$'s with different constant modified potentials such that E_n (energy) is the same for all like a thermodynamic constant. In order to retrieve Newton's picture, one must think in terms of rms values.

References

1. Ruggeri, Francesco R. Fermat's Principle, Particles with Rest Mass and Quantum Mechanics Part II (preprint, zenodo, 2022)
2. Ruggeri, Francesco R. Fermat's Principle, Particles with Rest Mass and Quantum Mechanics (preprint, zenodo, 2022)
3. Ruggeri, Francesco R. Time Base Force (Impulse) Versus Space Based Force $-dV/dx$ in Classical and Quantum Mechanics (preprint, zenodo, 2021)